

Synthesis of New Boron Compounds : Guanidine Boron Adduct and Hydroxamatoboron

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The synthesis of various boron compounds with hydroxamic acids and arylhydroxylamines has been reported¹. Two new hydroxylamine derivatives of boron along with a boron derivatives of guanidine have been synthesized. The different desired compounds have been prepared by the interaction of boric acid with a new complexing agent hydroxybiguanide, salicylhydroxamic acid and guanidine base respectively, to study their nature of bonding with boron(III).

Results and Discussion

The reactions between boric acid and hydroxybiguanidohydrochloride monohydrate (L_1) and salicylhydroxamic acid (L_2) respectively, producing boron heterocycles are presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

However, hot aqueous ethanolic solution of guanidine base in ethanol produce guanidine diboric acid adduct (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Hydroxybiguanidohydrochloride monohydrate (L_1) is a new ligand which has been characterized by analysis and ir studies.

The ir ligand bands at 3300–3420 cm^{-1} (NH_2 and H_2O) remain unchanged in the B-compounds, which indicates that the NH_2 group does not take part in coordination. The δ_{NH_2} ligand bands (~ 1600 – 1700 cm^{-1}) remain unchanged in the spectra of the boron compounds². The ν_{OH} modes occur as broad bands at 3100–3200 cm^{-1} as observed for boron heterocycles and adduct¹. B–O bands have been consistently found at 1180–1340 cm^{-1} . B–N band is observed at 1400–1470 cm^{-1} and in the region 720–780 cm^{-1} ³.

The compounds do not show any absorption in uv-region, which is in agreement with other biguanido and guanylurea compounds³. The molar conductance values of L_1 ($113.0 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and L_2 ($103.0 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) show that they are 1 : 1 electrolyte. The conductance of dihydroxyoxybiguanidoboron(III) hydrochloride monohydrate (HB) ($294.0 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicates that the Cl^- anion and two protons of the two OH groups attached to boron also ionize. So the compound behaves as 1 : 3 electrolyte. The molar conductance of hydroxy(salicylhydroxamato)boron(III) (SHB) ($52.0 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicates that ionization is incomplete in this case. The value of guanidine diboric acid adduct (GB) ($195.0 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicates that the compound is 1 : 2 electrolyte.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Solvents were purified whenever necessary. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1800 FTIR spectrophotometer. The conductance of the complexes was measured in H_2O solvent using an Elico CM82T conductivity bridge. Boron was estimated by the reported method⁴. N, C and H were estimated using a Perkin-Elmer 240C instrument. Chlorine was estimated gravimetrically⁵.

Hydroxybiguanidohydrochloride monohydrate (L_1) : A mixture of dicyandiamide and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 : 1) in tetrahydrofuran (THF) was refluxed for 3 h, then THF was evaporated. The residue was dissolved in ethanol-water mixture (1 : 1) and allowed to crystallize. The crystals were recrystallized from ethanol and finally dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride, (60%), m.p. 93–94° (Found : C, 14.10; H, 5.78; N, 40.98; Cl, 20.89. Calcd. for : C, 13.99; H, 5.87; N, 40.82; Cl, 20.66%); ν_{max} 3180 (OH), 3395 (NH_2), 1670 (δ_{NH_2}), 930 cm^{-1} (N–O).

Salicylhydroxamic acid (L₂) : $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHOH}$ (L_2) was synthesized by the interaction of ethyl ester of the acid with the free hydroxylamine according to the standard procedure⁶, m.p. 169°.

Dihydroxy(oxybiguanido)boron(III) hydrochloride monohydrate, C₂H₁₁N₃O₄BCl (HB) : A solution of boric acid (1.22 g) in hot water was added to ligand L_2 (1 : 1) in water and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The solution was then concentrated and on cooling the separated crystals were washed with ice-cold water-ethanol mixture (1 : 1) twice and with 90% ethanol. The compound was recrystallized from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride, (50%), m.p. 117–18° (Found : C, 11.32, H, 5.05; N, 32.68; B, 5.16; Cl, 16.64. Calcd. for : C, 11.14; H, 5.14; N, 32.51; B, 5.01; Cl, 16.45%); ν_{max} 3170 (OH), 3390 (NH₂) 1665 (δ_{NH_2}), 920 (N–O), 1340 (B–O), 720, 1460 cm^{-1} (B–N).

Hydroxy(salicylhydroxamato)boron(III), C₇H₆NO₄B (SHB) : A mixture of salicylhydroxamic acid (1.53 g) and boric acid (0.61 g) in hot water (1 : 1) was refluxed for 6 h. The solution was then concentrated and the resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol-water (1 : 1) mixture and dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride, (60%), m.p. 251–52° (Found : C, 47.12; H, 3.44; N, 7.94; B, 6.18. Calcd. for : C, 46.96; H, 3.37; N, 7.82; B, 6.04%); ν_{max} 3200 (OH), 890 (N–O), 1195 cm^{-1} (B–O).

Guanidine diboric acid adduct, CH₁₁N₃O₆B₂, (GB) : A mixture of an ethanolic solution of guanidine base (obtained from guanidine hydrochloride with calculated amount of NaOEt of ethanol) and hot aqueous solution of boric acid (1 : 1) was refluxed for 4 h, then concentrated by

evaporation and cooled. The resulting solid was washed with ice-cold water-ethanol mixture (1 : 1) twice and finally with dry ethanol. It was crystallized from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused calcium chloride, (50%), m.p. 300° (Found : C, 6.64; H, 6.18; N, 22.88; B, 12.04. Calcd. for : C, 6.56; H, 6.06; N, 22.97; B, 11.83%); ν_{max} 3175 (OH), 3420 (NH), 1700 (δ_{NH_2}), 1230 (B–O), 770, 1405 cm^{-1} (B–N).

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